

SOME REFLECTIONS ON THE PREVENTION OF VIOLENT CRIMES

Mukhiddinov Abror Hikmat Ugli

Associate Professor of the Department of Criminal Law at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Law, Associate Professor
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Abstract: The article examines the prevention of violent crimes. The causes of this type of crime and their social, economic, and psychological factors are analyzed. The importance of cooperation between state bodies, public organizations, and citizens in crime prevention is emphasized. Additionally, proposals aimed at preventive measures by law enforcement agencies, public education, and raising the legal awareness of the population are presented. The goal is to develop effective preventive mechanisms that serve to reduce violent crimes.

Keywords: Violent crimes, prevention, law enforcement, social factors, legal awareness, public cooperation, educational measures.

World experience shows that the legal, political, and socio-economic stability of any state is primarily determined by the guarantee of the life, health, freedom, and inviolability of the individual. Preventing violent crimes is one of the priority tasks in the protection of human rights. The Constitution and the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan also establish strict liability measures for acts of violence against a person.

Nevertheless, practice shows that crimes related to the use of violence still have high rates in society, especially in the family-domestic environment and on the basis of personal relationships, which increases the need for effective organization of their prevention.

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for crimes with elements of violence in a number of articles. The criminal liability established by these articles covers not only physical, but also psychological violence. This means that the concept of violence is not limited to hitting and beating, but also includes actions such as threats, insults, and pressure.

Although theoretical approaches, victimological analyses, and legal proposals on this problem have been developed in studies on the prevention of violent crimes in our country (A.A.Otajanov, A.G.Zokirova, S.S.Niyozova, and others), the mechanism of its practical impact and the system of inter-organizational cooperation are not sufficiently perfect.

In particular, S.S.Niyazova in her research paid special attention to such aspects as determining the victimological directions of crime prevention, harmonizing them with international norms, and reducing the environment prone to crime. However, as noted in the research, the organizational and legal mechanisms and interaction of preventive institutions in this area are not sufficiently systematized.

According to the results of studies conducted within the framework of the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 24, 2018 No. PP-4075, domestic violence was noted as the most common category among violent crimes committed in the regions of the Fergana Valley. This situation shows that preventive measures should be mainly aimed at maintaining the family environment, personal relationships, and psychological balance.

For the prevention of violent crimes, the following comprehensive preventive approaches should be implemented:

1. Improvement of legislation:

broad and clear expression of the concept of violence in legislation;

development of special legal mechanisms for domestic violence;

creation of a regulatory framework for identifying and protecting victimological risk groups.

2. Social prevention:

conducting broad anti-violence campaigns through the mass media;

Formation of a culture of empathy, tolerance, and constructive communication through propaganda.

3. Individual prevention:

identification of persons prone to violence and conducting psychological and educational work with them;

Regular work with persons registered for preventive maintenance.

4. Victimological approach:

Identification of potential victims;

providing them with legal advice, means of protection, and assistance via helplines.

In the prevention of violent crimes, along with legal measures, social, psychoprophylactic, and educational mechanisms are also important. In this matter, it is necessary to establish an effective mechanism of interaction between government bodies, law enforcement agencies, educational institutions, and civil society institutions, to act on the basis of systematic monitoring and analysis.

If an intolerant attitude towards violence is not formed in society, various legal measures may not fully yield their results. Therefore, solving this problem in harmony with a scientific approach, moral responsibility, and legal guarantees is a pressing task of today.

References:

1. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 24, 2018 No. PP-4075,

